

Inferring Interfaces of Encapsulated Libraries for Symbolic Execution

The Linux Kernel as a Case Study

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Abstract. *Symbolic execution* is an effective technique for identifying faults in real-world software and generating tricky test cases. Unfortunately, it does not scale well enough to handle programs that use large, complicated, libraries. As a result, symbolic execution of such programs either utilizes manually crafted models of the libraries or forgo symbolic information and executes library code concretely.

We propose a partial remedy to this problem in the form of a novel approach for *automatic inference of precise-enough* symbolically-executable specifications of encapsulated low-level libraries, i.e., pointer-manipulating libraries that maintain a strict separation between their own memory and that of their clients, e.g., the Linux kernel. Technically, we combine pointer analysis with numerical analysis to compute conservative input/output summaries of the way a library accesses the memory of its clients. The summaries are translated into specifications that are used by the symbolic execution engine to efficiently explore user applications and to identify potential faults. Our key insight is that the fiercely maintained encapsulation boundaries between the library memory state and the client memory state, e.g., the separation between kernel-space memory and user-space memory, makes it possible to automatically infer a precise-enough specification of the system calls interface. Our work is novel in that it leverages the design of the library memory protection mechanism, e.g., the restricted way the kernel manipulates user-space memory, to make the library analysis both practical, precise, and, assuming that the library code is correct, also sound.

We implemented our approach and evaluated it using a variety of applications interacting with the Linux kernel as our main case study. Our empirical evaluation demonstrates that our method is effective in terms of the small number of false positives, identifying new faults, and improving test coverage. We also demonstrate that our approach can be used to enable symbolic execution of applications using the BIO interface of the `openssl` library and of applications which interact with libraries running inside secure enclaves.

1 Introduction

Symbolic execution (SE) [20, 41] is an automated technique for evaluating the behavior of a program on all possible inputs. It has been successfully used for

test generation [32], for finding bugs [15], and for discovering security vulnerabilities [40]. (For an extended survey, see [16].) The idea behind symbolic execution was introduced almost 40 years ago [41]. However, in the last decade, symbolic execution gained new momentum due to the dramatic improvement in SMT solvers [25], and the invention of concolic testing and dynamic symbolic execution [4, 5, 7, 9, 12, 13, 19, 28, 32, 37, 42, 53, 55–58, 62, 63].

At a high level, symbolic execution engines systematically explore a program by maintaining a *symbolic state* per possible execution path. This state records the values of variables and heap-allocated locations as functions of the input. The program’s input is symbolic values. Every time the SE engine reaches a conditional jump, it clones the symbolic states and continues to explore both branches. The condition of the jump, or its negation, is added to the state’s *path condition*. The latter is a conjunction of quantifier-free first-order formulas that track the sequence of branches the SE engine chose to follow. To determine the feasibility of the path, SE engines utilize *satisfiability-modulo theory* (SMT) solvers [25]: Any satisfying assignment for a path condition translates directly into a test case that exercises the corresponding program path.

Unfortunately, despite the recent progress in scaling symbolic executions (see §10), applying symbolic tools to complicated applications is still a challenge. This is not surprising given the complicated nature of software and the SE engine’s precise modeling of the program behavior. Often, the bottleneck of symbolic execution occurs in complicated loops in the library code. This prevents the tool from identifying bugs in (even relatively simple) client applications as the symbolic exploration gets lost in the internals of the library [8, 39].

In this paper, we investigate the idea of modular symbolic execution with the motivation to identify faults in clients of complicated libraries and improve test coverage. More specifically, we use static analysis algorithms to infer an over-approximation of the input/output behavior of procedures, which we turn into *symbolically-executable specifications* of the library interface procedures, and then modify the symbolic execution engine to utilize the inferred specifications in the analysis of the client. In principle, our method can be applied to summarize the effect of arbitrary libraries. Moreover, our static analysis scales well to handle realistic libraries. However, in general our static analysis may not be precise enough due to the complexity of library code and thus can lead to plethora of false alarms. Surprisingly, we found that if we consider fully encapsulated low-level system libraries, e.g., the Linux kernel which provides system-level services to user-applications via the system call interface, then our analysis can be precise enough, as we validated using a few real-life client applications.

Our key insight is that while the library’s code is quite complex, its interactions with the client’s state is often rather restricted and follow self-imposed conventions that can be leveraged to make it amenable to static analysis. For example, the Linux kernel is extremely careful when following pointers into user-space memory. Specifically, every system call checks that its pointer parameters refer to user-space memory regions which the application is allowed to write to or read from. Hence, we can lift these self-imposed restrictions to perform

pointer analysis [35, 61] of the kernel in a rather crude way by ignoring most of the complications in its code. Similar restrictions, though less sophisticated, can be found in other low-level system libraries, e.g., openssl and libraries running inside secure enclaves. Indeed, one of the hallmarks of encapsulated low level libraries is that they employ various mechanisms to validate that accessing the memory regions received as parameters does not harm the integrity of their own memory state. The programmers implementing these libraries are expected to utilize these mechanisms before accessing the application’s memory state. Thus, *if* the library is implemented correctly, we may assume that every such access is preceded by an appropriate check, and utilize this assumption to obtain a conservative overapproximation of the behavior of *well-behaved* libraries.

We note that while the idea of combining static and symbolic analysis is a natural and useful idea, see, e.g., [49, 67], our combination is unique and sidesteps some of the biggest hurdles for applying static analysis to real code. In particular, one of the main challenges for statically analyzing the code of a complicated library is inferring precise aliasing information [34]. Our method does not try to perform a sound and precise pointer analysis of the library’s code, since this is a difficult task that we are trying to avoid. Instead, our analysis leverages the design of the library’s memory protection mechanism and *assumes* that the library utilizes this mechanism correctly to perform a lightweight static analysis. We found that the whose results are sufficiently precise to enable symbolic execution of client code with few false alarms. Specifically, our analysis of the library is not sound with respect to the standard C semantics as it is not aimed to identify bugs in the library. However, *if* the library’s code respects its design guidelines then the results of the analysis are in fact sound.

Main contributions. This paper makes the following technical contributions.

1. We define a new non-standard operational semantics for well-behaved library code (§4). Our semantics follows general ansi-c [36] requirements and generic memory protection coding conventions. This semantics precisely captures our assumptions on the library code.
2. We explain how to instrument the non-standard semantics in order to track properties required for our specifications (§5) and define a new static analysis, which overapproximates the instrumented semantics (§6). Our analysis is thus sound with respect to the non-standard semantics. The usage of this semantics shows how to benefit from system design to make static analysis better by avoiding the need to handle complicated code and tricky C semantics.
3. We describe an algorithm that utilizes the static analysis to generate procedure contracts (summaries) that can be used in any SE engine that provides certain services (§7).
4. We describe how to instantiate the generic memory protection coding conventions for the Linux kernel, `libc`, the BIO interface of the openssl library, and libraries running in secure enclaves (§8).

5. We modified KLEE [13]—a state of the art symbolic checker—to expose the necessary services and implemented our approach on top of it in a publicly available tool.
6. Our empirical evaluation, which focuses on applications of the Linux kernel, demonstrates that our method is effective in terms of the small number of false positives, identifying new faults, and improving test coverage (§9). We note that some of the new bugs that our analysis found in applications used in production were already fixed by the application developers.

We start by describing the memory protection mechanism employed by the Linux kernel (§2) and provide an informal overview of our approach (§3).

2 A Bird’s-Eye View of the System Calls Interface to the Linux Kernel

This section describes the way system calls treat application pointers, placing a special emphasis on the memory protection mechanism they use. Our analysis takes advantage of this defensive design to make the problem of determining which client memory locations system calls access tractable.

Linux programs execute in *kernel mode* or *user mode*. Kernel mode is reserved to the *kernel*, which is the core of the operating system and has unrestricted access to the hardware. User applications, e.g., web-browsers, web-servers, and database systems, run in user mode. This restricts their ability to access certain parts of the memory and prevents direct communication with the hardware. *System calls* provide the primary interface between user applications and the Linux kernel by acting as messengers: user applications issue requests by invoking system calls, and the kernel fulfills them or returns an error code [43]. Currently, Linux has over 300 system calls. Typically, applications invoke system calls indirectly via the standard C library (`libc`), which mostly does little work other than marshaling parameters into the right format.

System calls provide an austere interface: Their inputs are (arrays of) primitive values or (arrays of) records, e.g., C `structs`, whose pointer fields point to primitive types, and they return a `long`-typed value that indicates success or failure. (Often, but not always, a zero return value signifies success while a negative return value indicates failure.) Funneling the interaction between the user application and the hardware through the interface provided by the system calls is vital in ensuring a stable system: Every time a system call is invoked, it checks the *validity* of its pointer parameters (*user pointers*), i.e., whether the memory locations they refer to may be read from or write to by the application. Checking the validity of user pointers is crucial because system calls run in kernel-mode, and processing invalid user-supplied input might compromise the security and stability of the operating system.

Technically, the kernel distinguishes between two kinds of memory areas: *user-space* and *kernel-space*. The former may be accessed directly by user applications. The latter is accessible only to programs running in kernel mode. Before

following a pointer into user-space, the kernel consults its internal data structures to ensure that the pointers the user provided point to allocated regions of user-space memory that the application is permitted to access.

As a fiercely followed convention, parameters of kernel procedures which may point to user-space memory are annotated with a `__user` tag. Before dereferencing a `__user`-tagged user pointer (`addr`), the kernel validates the pointer by calling the function `access_ok(type,addr,size)`. The latter is also told whether the kernel intends to perform a *read access* or a *write access* (`type`) and the maximal number of bytes that may be accessed starting from `addr` (`size`). There are several kernel functions that wrap `access_ok` and allow a concise syntax for safe transfer of information between user-space and kernel-space. In particular, the following procedures, implemented in Fig. 1, are ubiquitous:

- `copy_to_user(uto,kfrom,n)` copies `n` bytes from the kernel-space memory area pointed-to by `kfrom` to the (user-space) buffer pointed to by `uto`.
- `copy_from_user(kto,ufrom,n)`, analogously, copies `n` bytes from the user-space buffer pointed-to by `ufrom` to the kernel-space memory area pointed-to by `kto`.

Both procedures return zero on success and the number of bytes they failed to copy on error. We note that it is standard for a system call to return `-EFAULT` if it is asked to follow an invalid pointer, i.e., one which does not point to a memory area the application is allowed to access.

```
1  ulong  copy_to_user(void __user *uto, const void * kfrom ,
2         ulong n){
3     if (!access_ok(VERIFY_WRITE, uto, n)) return n;
4     memcpy(uto, kfrom, n); return 0 }

5  ulong  copy_from_user(void *kto, const void __user * ufrom ,
6         ulong n){
7     if (!access_ok(VERIFY_READ, ufrom, n)) return n;
8     memcpy(kto, ufrom, n); return 0 }
```

Fig. 1. Simplified code of `copy_to/from_user()`. `ulong` is a shorthand for unsigned long.

It is a strict design decision that kernel code never blindly follows a pointer into user-space; it should always use `copy_to/from_user()`. System calls often use these procedures to transfer data to (resp. from) kernel-space before (resp. after) invoking the core kernel procedures that do the actual work. This programming idiom frees the core of the kernel from the need to validate pointer arguments. The exceptions to this idiom are scatter-gather operations, which are used to transfer multiple data arrays efficiently. However, the relevant system calls first employ `access_ok` to validate their arguments. See §??.

3 Overview

This section presents our running example and provides an informal explanation of our approach for generating and utilizing symbolically-executable contracts.

3.1 Running Example

```
1 long getrandom(                               1 main() {
2   char __user *f, uint s, uint fl) {        2   char b[4];
3   char *q = f, tmp[10];                    3   char *h = (char*) malloc(4);
4   int n = s, i, rv;                        4   int r1=0, r2=0;
5   ...                                       5   r1 = getrandom(b, sizeof(b), 0);
6   if (s == 0) return 0; L0:                6   r2 = getrandom(h, sizeof(h), 0);
7   if (512 < s) n = 512;                    7   assert (    r1 < 0
8   rv = n;                                   8           || r2 < 0
9   while (n) { ...                          9           || r1 == r2); }
10  extract_buf(tmp);
11  i = min(n,10);
12  L1: if (copy_to_user(q, tmp, i))
13      L2: return -EFAULT; L3:
14  L4: n = n - i; q = q + i; }
15  ...
16  return rv; L5: }
```

Fig. 2. A simplified code of the system call `getrandom()` and a user application using it.

Fig. 2 shows a simplified version of `getrandom(f,s,fl)`, a system call used to generate random numbers, and a simple user application that uses it. For clarity, we omit a large portion of the system call code, which computes the random values but does not interact with user-space memory. (We note that our analysis works on the original kernel code.)

The system call receives a pointer `f` to a user-space buffer, which is expected to be of size `s` bytes or more, and a flag `fl` which controls the way random bytes are generated. It sets `n` to be the minimum between `s` and 512, which is the maximal number of random bytes that a single call to `getrandom()` is allowed to compute. Then, `n` random bytes are computed by repeatedly invoking `extract_buf()`. The latter computes ten random bytes into a kernel-space buffer `tmp`, which the system call copies into the input user-space buffer starting at the position pointed-to by `q`. (Note that `i`, the number of copied bytes, is the minimum between the `n` random bytes left to generate and 10.) If the buffer is not big enough, `getrandom()` returns `-EFAULT`, as is customary in these cases. Otherwise, it advances the pointer `q` by `i` bytes, and updates `n` to the number of random bytes remaining to compute. When the loop terminates, `getrandom()` returns the number of random bytes it transferred to user-space.

Procedure `main()` is a client application using `getrandom()`. It invokes the system call twice. The first time, it passes a four byte-long stack-allocated array. The second time, it uses a four byte-long heap-allocated array. Finally, it asserts that both invocations compute the same number of random bytes, unless at least one of them failed. The procedure contains a subtle bug that manifests itself on 64-bit architectures but not on 32-bit ones: The call `sizeof(b)` returns four, which is the size of the stack allocated array. The call `sizeof(h)` returns the size of the pointer, which on 64-bit architecture is eight bytes. Our static analysis (§6) infers that `getrandom()` might write to the *s-1th* memory location after `h`, which allows the symbolic execution to warn that (on 64-bit architectures) the second invocation may lead to a buffer overrun.

3.2 Static Analysis of Well-Behaved System Calls

Static analysis is a technique for reasoning about all execution paths and all possible inputs of a given program. Technically, this is achieved by finitely representing (unbounded and possibly infinite) sets of program states by so-called *abstract states*, which abstract away details from the concrete program states. Employing abstraction can lead to an analysis that is more scalable than symbolic execution, but often less precise, thus resulting in false alarms.

Our analysis, described in §6, is a combination of a specialized pointer analysis and a numerical analysis: Every abstract state maintains, for each pointer variable p , a points-to set, denoted by $p \mapsto \{b_1, \dots, b_k\}$, which represents a superset of the buffers that it may point to. A buffer can be a user buffer, passed as a parameter, the special buffer *kernel* to indicate kernel memory, or the special buffer *null* to indicate the value of the pointer is NULL. The abstract state maintains a function from all known pointers to the set of buffers they may point to. The state is updated when pointers are assigned and allocated. In addition, every abstract state maintains a set of linear inequalities which are used to track the offset of every pointer variable inside a *user buffer*.

The most interesting aspect of our analysis is that it *assumes* that the kernel code is written correctly and does not fault. This allows us to avoid analyzing in our running example the code of `extract_buf()`, since none of its arguments is annotated by `__user`. This assumption also helps us make the analysis more precise. For example, we assume the kernel procedures never dereference NULL-valued pointers. Thus, although we use a points-to analysis, we can sometimes perform *strong updates*, i.e., remove buffers from the points-to set of a variable. For instance, we remove the *null* buffer from the points-to set of a pointer variable after the kernel dereferences it. This assumption is justified because we are interested in inferring the specification of the system calls. These procedures are designed to be suspicious of their input parameters, and thus are written defensively. Note that we already leverage one key aspect of their design by using the memory validation operations to determine the kernel access pattern to user space.

Example 1. Let τ_f denote the buffer referenced by f upon entry to the running example (Fig. 2). The abstract states shown below are computed by the analysis of the running example

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{s}_{notok} &= \langle [f \mapsto \{\tau_f\}, q \mapsto \{\tau_f\}], \phi_1 \wedge \phi_2 \wedge \phi_3 \wedge \text{offset}_{f,q} + i > \text{size}_f \rangle \\ \mathbf{s}_{writeok} &= \langle [f \mapsto \{\tau_f\}, q \mapsto \{\tau_f\}], \phi_1 \wedge \phi_2 \wedge \phi_3 \wedge \text{offset}_{f,q} + i \leq \text{size}_f \rangle \\ \mathbf{s}_{Ret} &= \langle [f \mapsto \{\tau_f\}, q \mapsto \{\tau_f\}], \phi_1 \wedge \phi_2 \wedge \phi_4 \rangle \end{aligned}$$

at program points L_2 , L_4 , and L_5 , respectively. Where

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_1 &= 0 < rv \wedge rv \leq s \wedge rv \leq 512 \\ \phi_2 &= 0 \leq \text{offset}_{f,f} \wedge \text{offset}_{f,f} \leq \text{size}_f \\ \phi_3 &= 0 < i \wedge i \leq n \wedge n \leq rv \wedge \text{offset}_{f,q} - \text{offset}_{f,f} + n = rv \\ \phi_4 &= \text{res} = rv \wedge \text{offset}_{f,q} - \text{offset}_{f,f} = rv \wedge \text{offset}_{f,f} + s < \text{size}_f . \end{aligned}$$

denotes the result of the numerical analysis. Here, size_f stands for the size of the memory region into which the pointer variable f points and $\text{offset}_{f,q}$ records the offset of the pointer variable q from the beginning of the memory region into which f points to. Note that \mathbf{s}_{notok} results from an unsuccessful validation command, whereas $\mathbf{s}_{writeok}$ results from a successful one, and that \mathbf{s}_{Ret} abstracts the memory states which occur when the procedure returns successfully.

The constraints above contain local variables and are therefore not directly suitable to be used in a summary. To fix this, we project away the local variables¹ and use the resulting constraint to form our contracts (see §3.3). The constraints in \mathbf{s}_{notok} (after projecting away local variables) imply that $\text{offset}_{f,f} + s > \text{size}_f$ and the ones in \mathbf{s}_{Ret} imply the converse. Hence, the analysis manages to infer that memory validation *fails* if the buffer does not contain size bytes after f .²

Our analysis scales well because it analyzes each system call separately, using an intraprocedural flow-sensitive static analysis: We inline the bodies of invoked procedures that receive `_user` annotated parameters, and treat all other procedures as if they may modify the *kernel-space* memory in an arbitrary manner but do not access user-space memory. As a result, our analysis can focus on a rather thin layer of kernel code, namely system calls, rather than performing a full-blown analysis of core kernel functionality.

Technically, the analysis (see §6) abstracts a non-standard semantics, which assumes that every access to a user-space buffer is preceded by a memory validation operation, and is sound with respect to it. Technically, the analysis is a *reduced product* [22] combination of our (rather crude) points-to analysis and a numerical analysis based on the Polyhedra domain [23], which abstracts instrumented memory states that explicitly record the sizes of user-space buffer parameters and the offsets of pointer variables which point to them (see §5).

¹ Technically, we use the projection operation of the Polyhedra abstract domain.

² Note that f may point to the middle of an allocated memory region and not necessarily to its beginning.

3.3 Symbolically-Executable Contracts

Our contracts are C procedures integrated into the symbolic execution engine as surrogates for the respective implementations of system calls: We obtain *symbolically-executable contracts* by applying static analysis to a system call (see §6) and converting the results of the analysis into a C procedure that invokes the services of the underlying symbolic-execution engine (see §7).

Symbolic Execution Engine Services The integration of contracts leverages the fact that symbolic-execution engines allow annotating programs with calls to services that can inspect and manipulate a symbolic state, e.g., by assigning a symbolic value to a certain variable. Specifically, the contracts use these services to evaluate properties over the symbolic state to detect possible memory access violations and to update it to conservatively simulate the side-effects of the invoked system call. Our contracts rely on the symbolic execution engine to provide, for a given symbolic state, the services listed in Fig. 3. We note that the conditions in the contract can be evaluated effectively because of the precise modeling of the memory layout in symbolic states. For example, the addresses and sizes of allocated buffers and the values of pointer variables are represented explicitly by KLEE [13], the symbolic engine we use.

Operation	Meaning
<code>SE_warn(<i>s</i>)</code>	Emits the warning message <i>s</i> .
<code>SE_size(<i>p</i>)</code>	The size of the memory region <i>p</i> points to.
<code>SE_base(<i>p</i>)</code>	The base address of the memory region <i>p</i> points to.
<code>SE_valid(<i>p</i>)</code>	Checks if <i>p</i> is definitely a valid pointer, which means that the following holds: $p = \text{NULL} \vee (p \neq \text{NULL} \wedge 0 \leq p - \text{SE_base}(p) \leq \text{SE_size}(p))$.
<code>SE_assume(ϕ)</code>	Intersects the symbolic state with ϕ .
<code>SE_SAT(ϕ)</code>	Checks whether ϕ possibly holds.
<code>SE_assert(ϕ)</code>	Checks whether $\neg \text{SE_SAT}(\neg \phi)$ holds.
<code>SE_havoc(<i>p</i>)</code>	Replace the contents of the buffer <i>p</i> points to with an unconstrained symbolic value.

Fig. 3. Services of the symbolic execution engine.

Context Assumptions In order to increase precision and reduce the chance of false alarms, our contracts are invoked in a context-sensitive manner: We use a formula over the input arguments to encode a *context assumption*. A system call can be potentially associated with multiple contexts, where each context corresponds to a context-sensitive contract and a procedure that checks whether the assumption holds during symbolic execution (e.g., `getrandom_check_context_1`, shown in Fig. 4, checks that `f` points to an allocated memory location). In the analysis phases, the context assumption is used to set the initial abstract state. During symbolic execution, context assumptions are used to pick a contract

```

1 long getrandom_contract_1(char __user *f, uint s, uint fl) {
2   long res;
3   // 1. Auxiliary variables initialization
4   unsigned int size_f = SE_size(f);
5   int offset_f,f = f - SE_base(f);
6   // 2. Precondition (L2)
7   if (SE_SAT(0 < s ∧ 0 ≤ offset_f,f ∧ offset_f,f + s > size_f)) SE_warn("buffer
      overrun");
8   // 3. Modify (L4)
9   if (SE_SAT(0 < s ∧ 0 ≤ offset_f,f)) SE_havoc(f);
10  // 4. Postcondition
11  SE_assume( (s=0 ∧ res=0) // Postcondition (L0)
12    ∨ // Postcondition (L3)
13    (0 < s ∧ 0 ≤ offset_f,f ∧ offset_f,f + s ≥ size_f ∧ res = -EFAULT)
14    ∨ // Postcondition (L5)
15    (0 < s ∧ 0 ≤ offset_f,f ∧ offset_f,f + s < size_f ∧ 0 < res ∧ res ≤
      s ∧ res ≤ 512) );
16  return res; }

18 int getrandom_check_context_1(char __user *f, uint s, uint fl)
19   {
20   // Context assumptions
21   return SE_assert(SE_valid(f) ∧ f ≠ NULL); }

```

Fig. 4. The contract inferred for `getrandom`. For legibility, we only show key constraints. `res` records the return value.

among the contracts associated with a system call. We note that context assumptions do not affect soundness. If, upon entry to a syscall, no context assumption holds, the call is treated as unreachable by the symbolic execution engine, which may only reduce coverage. The context can be given by the user or inferred automatically from the symbolic state. In our experiments, we observed that we only needed the following, rather expected, context assumption: every pointer is valid (i.e., its address is within a memory region allocated by the user) and non-NULL, different pointers are not aliased, and that the size of a buffer is greater than 0.

Contracts Fig. 4 shows the contract generated for the running example. As any contract we generate, it is comprised of the following four elements.

1. Auxiliary Variables. In addition to the integer-typed parameters and constants that appear in the system call code (`s`, `fl`, and `512` in our example), our contracts use auxiliary variables to record the size of user-space memory regions (`size_`), and the offset of pointer variables (`offset_`) into them. The auxiliary variables are initialized once after validation, using the SE engine services, and are never re-assigned. We note that the initialization of the auxiliary variable is well-defined only when the corresponding pointer variables correspond to a particular aliasing pattern, e.g., $SE_base(f)$ has a meaningful value only when f points to an allocated memory region. The validity of the initialization is ensured by the context assumptions (see §3.3).

2. Precondition. Preconditions express a set of safe input states—states whose execution never results in a failed memory validation, i.e., in a user-induced failure. Our contracts include one condition per `access_ok` command (or its wrappers, e.g., `copy_to_user()` and `copy_from_user()`). Each condition overapproximates the set of states for which memory validation fails, therefore an input state that passes all the conditions must be safe. For `getrandom`, the precondition expresses a set of input states for which `copy_to_user(q, tmp, i)` (line 12) may return `false`. Specifically, the first conjunct is needed to reach the command, the second comes from the context assumptions, and the conjunct indicates that the validation fails when there is an attempt to access the buffer `f` beyond its upper limit. Technically, the preconditions are obtained from the numerical constraints computed after failed memory validation operations by projecting away the local variables.

3. Modification. One of the goals of replacing a system call with a contract is to allow the symbolic execution engine to “fast forward” over the code by directly updating the symbolic state. However, precisely summarizing the effect of writes to user buffers requires a complicated static analyses and often does not contribute useful information. We address this concern by treating writes abstractly. That is, for each user buffer, we infer an overapproximate condition on the set of input states that may lead to any write to that buffer. If the condition holds, the symbolic state is updated to reflect an arbitrary write to the buffer. This may lead to false alarms in cases where the content of the buffers is important, however, we have not encountered such cases in our experiments.

4. Postcondition. Postconditions express the *effect* of the system call by relating the return value to the input states. For example, the contract for `getrandom()` expresses the fact that if the inputs lead to a write beyond the upper limit of the buffer `f` then the result is `-EFAULT`, and to a positive number smaller than both 512 and `s`, otherwise.

3.4 Symbolic Execution with Contracts

The symbolic execution engine is adapted so that whenever it encounters an invocation of a system call P it picks the contract that satisfies its context assumption and executes P 's contract instead of its code. Fortunately, the engine can precisely check the type of constraints we use (that `f` is valid and `f` \neq `NULL`, see `getrandom_check_context_1` in Fig. 4). The engine then symbolically executes the contract as follows. First (phase 1 in in Fig. 4), it assigns values to the auxiliary variables. Second (phase 2), it checks that the precondition holds, and emits warnings for possible attempts to access `NULL`, or to access a user space location outside of the memory buffers passed as parameters (by the call to `copy_to_user` in our example). Third (phase 3), it uses `SE_havoc_cont` to express that the contents of potentially-modified buffers (`f` in our example) may change arbitrarily if the given conditions hold. Finally (phase 4), it ensures that the return value `res` satisfies the constraints found at the return site (to either 0, `-EFAULT`, or the minimum between `s` and 512, in our example).

4 Programming Language

In this section, we define a simple programming language for *well-behaved* system calls: We associate the language with a non-standard semantics, which includes assumptions to express the fact that a system call is well-behaved. We refer to this semantics as the *concrete semantics*. For space reasons, we defer details on treating arrays to §??.

Syntax For expository reasons, we abstract away from specific control-flow statements and simply assume the presence of one *control-flow graph* (CFG) per procedure. A CFG is comprised of a set of nodes N and a set of edges $ECmd \subseteq N \times Cmd \times N$, which are labeled by the primitive commands given below.

$$\begin{aligned}
 Cmd ::= & x := aexp \mid p := \text{NULL} \mid p := q + x \mid x := p - q \mid \text{assume}(x \bowtie y) \mid \text{assume}(p = q) \mid \text{assume}(p \neq q) \\
 & \mid x := \text{load}(p) \mid q := \text{load}(p) \mid p := \text{alloc}(s) \mid \text{return } x \\
 & \mid \text{read_ok}(p, s) \mid \text{read_notok}(p, s) \mid \text{write_ok}(p, s) \mid \text{write_notok}(p, s)
 \end{aligned}$$

Here, x and s are integer variables, p and q are pointer variables, $aexp$ is an integer-typed expression,³ and \bowtie is a relation symbol over integers, e.g., $<$. An expression of the form $p - q$ has an integer value, denoting the distance between the addresses of two pointer variables, provided they point to the same *memory*

³ For brevity, we leave the syntax of integer-typed expressions unspecified.

region (see below), and $q + x$ denotes the address at distance x from q , provided that the location at this address is in the memory region that q points to.

The meaning of the primitive commands is as follows: `assume` commands are used to implement conditionals. `alloc(s)` allocates a *memory region* comprised of $s+1$ consecutive memory locations,⁴ $x := \text{load}(p)$ resp. $q := \text{load}(p)$ retrieves the integer resp. pointer value stored at the memory location pointed-to by p . `store(p, x)` writes the value of x to the location that p points to. The command `read_ok(p, s)` validates that p points to a user-space memory location ℓ that the application can read from, as well as from locations $\ell + i$, for $i = 1..s-1$; and `write_ok(p, s)` does the same, but validates that the application is allowed to write to these locations. The commands `read_notok(p, s)` and `write_notok(p, s)` fire if the validation made by `read_ok(p, s)` and `write_ok(p, s)`, respectively, fails. The command `return x` is syntactic sugar for an assignment of the return value x to a designated local integer variable.

Notations and simplifying assumptions. In the rest of the paper, we assume that we are working with a fixed arbitrary system call P . We denote P 's pointer and integer formal parameters by $f \in \text{PTFormal}$ and $i \in \text{IFormal}$, respectively, and its pointer and integer local variables by $p \in \text{PTLocal}$ and $i \in \text{ILocal}$, respectively. (We expect that $\text{IFormal} \subseteq \text{ILocal}$ and $\text{PTFormal} \subseteq \text{PTLocal}$.) We assume, without loss of generality, that $\text{PTFormal} = \{f_1, \dots, f_k\}$, for some k , and that formal parameters are immutable. For brevity, we refer to the user-space regions referenced by (the immutable) pointer parameters as *buffers*.

A Semantics for Well-Behaved System Calls A *memory state* (*state*, for short) $\sigma = \langle n, \text{env}, h, A, R, W \rangle$ is comprised of the *current program point* $n \in N$, an *environment* env , a *store* h , a finite set of *allocated regions* A , a *read set* R , and a *write set* W . The second and third components of a state are standard ingredients of operational semantics for pointer programs. $\text{env} : \text{Var} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ is an *environment* mapping variables Var to their values. For simplicity, we only consider integer values. We represent *memory locations* $\ell \in \text{Loc}$ as positive natural numbers, i.e., $\text{Loc} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbb{N}^+$. The NULL value, which is not a valid memory location, is represented by zero. A *store* $h : A \rightarrow_{\text{fin}} \mathbb{Z}$ maps addresses of allocated memory locations to their values.

The components A, R, W are used to formalize our assumptions regarding the expected well-behavior of system calls: A *memory region* $r \in \text{Region} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{\{i..j\} \subset \text{Loc} \mid 0 < i \leq j\}$ is a finite set of consecutive locations. The component $A \subset_{\text{fin}} \text{Region}$ is a set of (non-overlapping) regions which records the allocated memory regions. We assume that memory locations are partitioned into kernel-

⁴ `alloc(s)` allocates $s + 1$ memory locations to ensure that the allocated region also includes the location right beyond the last accessible location in that region. Ansi C allows pointing to this location, but not to dereference it nor to go beyond it. Its inclusion in the allocated buffer ensures that it is not possible to traverse from one region to an adjacent one.

space $K \subset Loc$ and user-space $U \subset Loc$.⁵ An allocated region $r \in A$ is either in kernel-space or in user-space but cannot be in both. System calls run in kernel mode. Thus, they allocate memory in kernel-space. A pointer-typed parameter of a system call, on the other hand, may only point to be a user-space location. The sets $R \subset A$ and $W \subset A$ are the user-space memory regions that the kernel validated as readable and writable, respectively. Hence, every region $r \in R \cup W$ is contained in an allocated user-space region $r' \in A$, i.e., $r \subseteq r'$ and $r' \subset U$.

Notations. Let $\sigma = \langle n, env, h, A, R, W \rangle$ be a memory state. The *region of a memory location ℓ in σ* , denoted by $r_\sigma(\ell)$, is the (necessarily unique) region in A that ℓ belongs to, or the empty set if no such region exists. The *region of a pointer variable p in σ* , denoted by $r_\sigma(p) = r_\sigma(env(p))$, is the region of the location p points to. The *base address* of a pointer variable p in σ , denoted by $base_\sigma(p)$, is the lowest location in the region it points to, provided the latter is not empty. Technically, $base_\sigma(p) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (r_\sigma(p) \neq \emptyset) ? \min(r_\sigma(p)) : \perp$, where $b ? v_t : v_f$ stands for v_t , if b is true, and v_f otherwise. \perp is the undefined value. The *offset* of p in σ , denoted by $offset_\sigma(p)$, is its distance from its base address, i.e., $offset_\sigma(p) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} env(p) - base_\sigma(p)$. If $base_\sigma(p) = \perp$ then so is $offset_\sigma(p)$. We denote the store h of a state σ by h_σ and use a similar notation for other components.

Admissible states. A memory state $\sigma = \langle n, env, h, A, R, W \rangle$ is *admissible* if A is comprised of non-overlapping regions, every region $r \in A$ is either in user-space ($r \subset U$) or in kernel-space ($r \subset K$); the value of a pointer variable is either an allocated location or NULL; every writable region is also readable, i.e., $W \subseteq R$; and every validated region $r' \in R$ is contained in an allocated region $r \in A$. Furthermore, if n is the target of a successful validation command $cmd = \text{read_ok}(p, s)$ or $cmd = \text{write_ok}(p, s)$, then the locations $env(p)..env(p) + env(s)$ are contained in a user-space allocated region $r \in A$. If, on the other hand, n is the target of an unsuccessful validation command $cmd = \text{read_ok}(p, s)$ or $cmd = \text{write_ok}(p, s)$ then no such region r exists. We denote the set of admissible memory states by Σ . We note that our semantics preserves state admissibility.

We denote the targets of control-flow edges labeled with unsuccessful validation commands (i.e., `read_notok` and `write_notok`) by N_{notok} , the targets of successful write-validation commands (i.e., `write_ok`) by $N_{writeok}$, and the targets of return commands (i.e., `return x`) as N_{ret} . Without loss of generality, we assume that every node in $N_{notok} \cup N_{writeok} \cup N_{ret}$ has a single incoming edge.

Operational Semantics Fig. 5 formalizes the meaning of every primitive command cmd , which implicitly labels an edge (n, cmd, n') , as a state transformer $\llbracket cmd \rrbracket : \Sigma \rightarrow \wp(\Sigma)$. The meaning is rather standard, *with one major exception*: we assume that the kernel code is *well-behaved*. More specifically, we assume that kernel code never accesses a user-space location without first validating it. Thus,

⁵ In general, the analysis assumes a strict partitioning between the library memory state and the client memory state.

the semantics blocks attempts to read from or write to unallocated kernel-space locations or *unvalidated* user-space locations. This assumption coincides with the standard semantics for well-behave system calls, but allows for analyses using a very aggressive abstraction of the kernel-space memory without producing a large number of false alarms. Similarly, and for the same reasons, we expect that pointer arithmetics would be done according to the ansi C standard [36], i.e., the expression $p - q$ would be applied only to pointers to the same region and that the expression $p + x$ would form a pointer into p 's region. These assumptions are formalized by the side-conditions of the commands `load`, `store`, $p := q + x$, and $x := p - q$ commands.

Example 2. Consider the side-condition of $p := q + x$ and `read_ok(p, s)`. The side-condition of $p := q + x$ validates that the pointer formed by adding x to q points to the same region as q . Specifically, if q points to an array, then p is guaranteed to point to an element in the array or to the memory right beyond the last element in that array. According to the ansi C standard [36], an attempt to form a pointer to any other location leads to an undefined behavior. Our semantics, which assumes that the kernel code is well-behaved, simply blocks the execution if such an attempt is made.⁴ Consider, for example, the abstract state $\mathbf{s}_{writeok}$ shown in Example 1, computed at L_4 in our running example. In this state, q points to the same buffer as f . Our non-standard semantics of $p := q + x$ allows us to conclude that after q is advanced by i bytes, it still points to the same buffer.

The side-condition for $x := \text{load}(p)$ ensures that the memory location p points to is located in kernel-space ($env(p) \in \bigcup A \cap K$) or was validated as user-space readable ($env(p) \in R$). This also filters out states in which the kernel attempts, e.g., to dereference a NULL-valued pointer. The semantics does so because we are not interested in validating the correctness of the kernel. Setting up the semantics this way allows for a very aggressive abstraction of the contents of the kernel-space memory (see §6). The side-condition for $q := \text{load}(p)$ is stricter: it also requires that the value read is either an allocated location or NULL and that user-space locations do not point into kernel-space. The command `read_ok(p, s)` validates that the location pointed to by p , together with the s locations following it, are allocated in user space. This is done by checking that A contains a user-space region ($V_{p,s+1} \subset U$) that includes the validated locations. Note that a successful validation does not allow to access the last location in a region.⁶ The other validation commands work in a similar way. The command `read_notok(p, s)` fires if $V_{p,s+1}$ is *not* contained in an allocated user-space region. The side-condition encodes our assumption that the kernel only validates pointers to user-space memory. The commands `write_ok(p, s)` and `write_notok(p, s)` work in a similar way to `read_ok(p, s)` and `read_notok(p, s)`.

⁶ This is due to the “first location beyond and array” that ansi C [36] allows pointing to, but not accessing.

Lemma 1. Let $\sigma \in \Sigma$ be an admissible state and cmd a command. For any $\sigma' \in \llbracket cmd \rrbracket \sigma$, the following holds: (i) σ' is admissible, i.e., $\sigma' \in \Sigma$; (ii) the allocation, read and write sets never shrink, i.e., $A_\sigma \subseteq A_{\sigma'}$, $R_\sigma \subseteq R_{\sigma'}$, $W_\sigma \subseteq W_{\sigma'}$; (iii) any location ℓ in σ' which is not allocated in A_σ is in kernel space, i.e., if $\ell \notin A_{\sigma'} \setminus A_\sigma$ then $\ell \in K$; (iv) the value stored in a user-space location may change only if the location has been validated as writable, i.e., if $\ell' \in U \setminus W_{\sigma'}$ then $h_{\sigma'}(\ell') = h_\sigma(\ell')$; and (v) user-space locations do not store pointers to kernel-space.

Command	Resulting set of states	Side Conditions
$\llbracket x := aexp \rrbracket \sigma$	$\{\langle n', env[x \mapsto \llbracket aexp \rrbracket \sigma], h, A, R, W \rangle\}$	
$\llbracket p := \text{NULL} \rrbracket \sigma$	$\{\langle n', env[p \mapsto 0], h, A, R, W \rangle\}$	
$\llbracket p := q + x \rrbracket \sigma$	$\{\langle n', env[p \mapsto env(q) + env(x)], h, A, R, W \rangle\}$	$env(q) + env(x) \in r_\sigma(q)$
$\llbracket x := p - q \rrbracket \sigma$	$\{\langle n', env[x \mapsto env(p) - env(q)], h, A, R, W \rangle\}$	$env(q) \in r_\sigma(p)$
$\llbracket \text{assume}(bexp) \rrbracket \sigma$	$\{\langle n', env, h, A, R, W \rangle\}$	$\llbracket bexp \rrbracket \sigma = \text{true}$
$\llbracket p := \text{alloc}(s) \rrbracket \sigma$	$\{\langle n', env[p \mapsto \ell], h, A \cup \{r\}, R, W \rangle\}$	$r = \{\ell.. \ell + env(s)\} \subseteq K \wedge r \cap \bigcup A = \emptyset$
$\llbracket x := \text{load}(p) \rrbracket \sigma$	$\{\langle n', env[v \mapsto h(env(p))], h, A, R, W \rangle\}$	$env(p) \in (\bigcup A \cap K) \cup R$
$\llbracket q := \text{load}(p) \rrbracket \sigma$	$\{\langle n', env[q \mapsto h(env(p))], h, A, R, W \rangle\}$	$env(p) \in (\bigcup A \cap K) \cup R \wedge$ $h(env(p)) \in \bigcup A \cup \{0\} \wedge$ $(env(p) \in U \implies h(env(p)) \notin K)$
$\llbracket \text{store}(p, v) \rrbracket \sigma$	$\{\langle n', env, h[env(p) \mapsto env(v)], A, R, W \rangle\}$	$env(p) \in (\bigcup A \cap K) \cup W$
$\llbracket \text{read_ok}(p, s) \rrbracket \sigma$	$\{\langle n', env, h, A, R \cup \{V_{p,s}\}, W \rangle\}$	$V_{p,s+1} \subseteq U \wedge \exists r \in A. V_{p,s+1} \subseteq r$
$\llbracket \text{read_notok}(p, s) \rrbracket \sigma$	$\{\langle n', env, h, A, R, W \rangle\}$	$V_{p,s+1} \subseteq U \wedge \nexists r \in A. V_{p,s+1} \subseteq r$
$\llbracket \text{write_ok}(p, s) \rrbracket \sigma$	$\{\langle n', env, h, A, R \cup \{V_{p,s}\}, W \cup \{V_{p,s}\} \rangle\}$	$V_{p,s+1} \subseteq U \wedge \exists r \in A. V_{p,s+1} \subseteq r$
$\llbracket \text{write_notok}(p, s) \rrbracket \sigma$	$\{\langle n', env, h, A, R, W \rangle\}$	$V_{p,s+1} \subseteq U \wedge \nexists r \in A. V_{p,s+1} \subseteq r$

Fig. 5. The concrete meaning of primitive commands, labeling a control-flow edge (n, cmd, n') , and applied to a state $\sigma = \langle n, env, h, A, R, W \rangle$. We denote the meaning of an expression exp by $\llbracket exp \rrbracket \sigma$. We write $V_{p,s} \{env(p)..env(p) + env(s)\}$ and $V_{p,s+1} V_{p,s} \cup \{env(p) + env(s) + 1\}$ for the regions starting at p and spanning p and $p + 1$ locations, respectively.

5 An Instrumented Semantics for Specification Inference

This section defines the instrumented semantics, which extends the concrete semantics with auxiliary variables. The static analysis (§6) keeps track of these variables, and their necessity will become apparent in §7.

Instrumented States To enable an analysis to infer the type of specifications we need, we make the integer values, over which numeric constraints are defined, explicit. We do so by defining the following *instrumentation variables* and instrumenting the concrete semantics to track their values.

- *Buffer sizes*: We maintain an immutable integer-typed variable for every pointer-typed argument f , to stand for the size of its buffer: $Sizes \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{size_f \mid f \in PTFormal\}$.

- *Pointer offsets*: We maintain, for each pointer-typed argument f and pointer p , the distance of p from the first address of f 's buffer: $Offset \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{offset_{f,p} \mid p \in PTLocal, f \in PTFormal\}$.

We expect \cdot , without loss of generality, $ILocal$, $Sizes$, and $Offset$ to be pairwise disjoint. The *instrumented states*, denoted by $\hat{\Sigma}$, are defined the same way as the concrete states, except that an environment $e\hat{nv} : \hat{V}ar \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ ranges over the instrumented set of variables $\hat{V}ar \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} Var \cup Sizes \cup Offset$. To avoid clutter, we use the same notation σ for concrete and instrumented states.

$$\begin{array}{l}
\text{Inst}[\text{cmd}] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} [\text{cmd}] \circ \text{Inst}'[\text{cmd}], \text{ where} \\
\text{Inst}'[x := aexp] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} [\text{skip}] \qquad \text{Inst}'[p := \text{alloc}(s)] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} [offset_{f,p} := \perp \mid f \in PTFormal] \\
\text{Inst}'[p := \text{NULL}] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} [offset_{f,p} := \perp \mid f \in PTFormal] \qquad \text{Inst}'[q := \text{load}(p)] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} [offset_{f,q} := \top \mid f \in PTFormal] \\
\text{Inst}'[p := q + x] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} [offset_{f,p} := offset_{f,p} + x \mid f \in PTFormal] \qquad \text{Inst}'[q := \text{store}(p, v)] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} [\text{skip}] \\
\text{Inst}'[\text{assume}(x \bowtie y)] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} [\text{assume}(\hat{x} \bowtie \hat{y})] \qquad \text{Inst}'[ok(p, s)] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} [\text{assume}(offset_{f,p} + s < size_f)] \\
\text{Inst}'[\text{assume}(p = \text{NULL})] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} [offset_{f,p} := \perp \mid f \in PTFormal] \qquad \text{Inst}'[notok(p, s)] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} [\text{assume}(offset_{f,p} + s \geq size_f)]
\end{array}$$

Fig. 6. Instrumented semantics. $[\text{cmd} \mid \text{condition}]$ stands for the parallel application of a set of conditional assignments. *ok* stands for `read_ok` and `write_ok`, and *notok* stands for `read_notok` and `write_notok`.

Instrumented Semantics We express the instrumented semantics via the state transformer $\text{Inst}[\text{cmd}] : \hat{\Sigma} \rightarrow \wp(\hat{\Sigma})$, defined in Fig. 6, except for the most interesting cases, which are shown below. We lift the concrete state transformer to sets of instrumented states in a point-wise manner: $[\text{cmd}] : \wp(\hat{\Sigma}) \rightarrow \wp(\hat{\Sigma})$. The transformers first apply the concrete semantics $[\text{cmd}]$ to update the concrete state and then update the instrumentation variables via an *instrumentation command* \hat{cmd} . The instrumented semantics is carefully defined to enable a numerical analysis to generate the numeric constraints needed for the specification. The instrumentation variables are updated based only on their current values, with the following exceptions:

For `assume` ($p = q$) and `assume` ($p \neq q$), updating the offset variables requires knowing which buffers the pointers reference. We determine that, say, p points to buffer f by checking that its offset in f is not \perp (not that the semantics ensures that if p and q point to memory locations then these have to be in the same memory region):

$$\begin{array}{l}
\text{Inst}'[\text{assume}(p = q)] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} [\text{assume}(\bigwedge_{f \in PTFormal} \phi_{p=q}^f)] \\
\text{where } \phi_{p=q}^f \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (offset_{f,p} \neq \perp \wedge offset_{f,q} \neq \perp) \implies offset_{f,p} = offset_{f,q}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
\text{Inst}'[\text{assume}(p \neq q)] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} [\text{assume}(\bigwedge_{f \in PTFormal} \phi_{p \neq q}^f)] \\
\text{where } \phi_{p \neq q}^f \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (offset_{f,p} \neq \perp \wedge offset_{f,q} \neq \perp) \implies offset_{f,p} \neq offset_{f,q}.
\end{array}$$

For $x := p - q$, we overwrite the value of x in case p and q point to a buffer passed as a parameter. This does not change the value of x , but allows for

more precise analysis as we only track offsets of variables pointing into buffer parameters.

$$\text{Inst}'[x := p - q] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \llbracket x := \exists f \in \text{PTFormal}. \text{offset}_{f,p} \neq \perp \rrbracket ? \text{offset}_{f,p} - \text{offset}_{f,q} : x$$

We define the *extraction function* $\hat{\beta}: \Sigma \rightarrow \hat{\Sigma}$ for a concrete state $\sigma = \langle n, \text{env}, h, A, R, W \rangle$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\beta}(\langle n, \text{env}, h, A, R, W \rangle) &= \langle n, \hat{\text{env}}, h, A, R, W \rangle \\ \hat{\text{env}} &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \lambda x \in \hat{\text{Var}}. \begin{cases} \text{env}(x) & x \in \text{Var} \\ |r_\sigma(f)| - 1 & x = \text{size}_f \\ \text{offset}_\sigma(p) & x = \text{offset}_{f,p} \wedge r_\sigma(p) = r_\sigma(f) \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Example 3. Consider the inner loop of `getrandom` (Fig. 2). The instrumented values are $\hat{\text{env}}(n) = \text{env}(n)$ and $\hat{\text{env}}(i) = \text{env}(i)$ for local variables. $\hat{\text{env}}(\text{size}_f) = |r_\sigma(f)| - 1$ for the size of f , and is constant during the execution of `getrandom`. In the first iteration, at location L_1 , the offset is $\hat{\text{env}}(\text{offset}_{f,q}) = 0$. After the first iteration of the loop, at location L_1 , the offset changes to be as follows: $\hat{\text{env}}(\text{offset}_{f,q}) = 10$ if $\hat{\text{env}}(n) > 10$ and $\hat{\text{env}}(\text{offset}_{f,q}) = \hat{\text{env}}(n)$, otherwise.

Theorem 1 follows immediately from the definition of the instrumented semantics.

Theorem 1 (Bisimulation). *For every concrete state σ and primitive command cmd , we have that $\sigma' \in \llbracket \text{cmd} \rrbracket \sigma$ if and only if $\hat{\beta}(\sigma') \in \text{Inst}[\text{cmd}] \hat{\beta}(\sigma)$ holds.*

6 Static Analysis of Well-Behaved System Calls

We now formally define the static analysis used in our method. Formally, the analysis is an abstract interpretation of the instrumented semantics defined in §5. Recall that the latter is a bisimulation of the concrete semantics of our programming language, defined in §4 (See theorem 1).

6.1 Region Analysis

Abstract domain. Our pointer analysis determines a superset of the possible regions that each pointer variable may target. This is achieved by employing the following *region abstract domain*:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{PTDom} &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \langle \text{PTEnv}, \perp_{PT}, \sqcup_{PT} \rangle \\ \text{PTEnv} &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{PTLocal} \rightarrow \wp(\text{ARegs}) \quad \perp_{PT} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \lambda x. \emptyset \quad \sqcup_{PT} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \lambda pt, pt'. (\lambda x \in \text{PTLocal}. pt(x) \cup pt'(x)) \\ &\text{where } \text{ARegs} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{ABuffers} \cup \{\mathbf{r}_K, \mathbf{r}_U, \mathbf{r}_N\} \text{ and } \text{ABuffers} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{\mathbf{r}_f \mid f \in \text{PTFormal}\} \end{aligned}$$

An *abstract region environment* $pt \in \text{PTEnv}$ maps each pointer-typed variable p to its *points-to set* $pt(p)$ —a (bounded sub)set of *abstract regions*, ARegs . An abstract region is either \mathbf{r}_f , where f is a pointer-typed formal parameter, representing the buffer referenced by f ; \mathbf{r}_K , representing the entire kernel space;

τ_U , representing the entire user-space, excluding the buffers; or τ_N , representing NULL.

We define an *abstraction function* $\alpha_{PT}: \wp(\hat{\Sigma}) \rightarrow PTEnv$ using an abstraction function for *single* instrumented states $\beta_{PT}: \hat{\Sigma} \rightarrow PTEnv$.

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{PT}(X) &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sqcup_{PT} \{ \beta_{PT}(\delta) \mid \delta \in X \} \\ \beta_{PT}(\delta) &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \lambda p \in PTLocal. (R_\delta(p) \neq \emptyset) ? R_\delta(p) : \{ \tau_U \} \cup \{ \tau_N \mid env(p) = \text{NULL} \} \cup \{ \tau_K \mid env(p) \in K \} \\ &\text{where } R_\delta(p) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{ \tau_f \mid \text{base}_\sigma(p) = \text{base}_\delta(f) \wedge f \in PTLocal \} . \end{aligned}$$

This induces a concretization function $\gamma_{PT}: PTEnv \rightarrow \wp(\hat{\Sigma})$ in the standard way:

$$\gamma_{PT}(pt) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{ \delta \mid \beta_{PT}(\delta) \sqcup_{PT} pt = pt \} .$$

Abstract transformers. Fig. 7 defines the vanilla abstract transformers $PTv[cmd]: PTEnv \rightarrow PTEnv$ for every command cmd . The transformers are specialized to well-behaved system calls as follows. The side-conditions in Fig. 5 implicitly ensure that on every access to a pointer variable p (either for loading, or pointer arithmetic), the pointer is non-NULL. The abstract transformers reflect this by removing τ_N from the points-to set of p . The memory validation commands, for a pointer p , ensure that the validated region is not in kernel-space. This is reflected by removing τ_K from the points-to set of p . A command of the form $q := \text{load}(p)$ reads an address stored at the location ℓ that p points to. The read value v must be either NULL or any memory location, except that v cannot be the address of a kernel-space location if ℓ is in user-space. This is because such addresses are never stored in user-space. Finally, we employ the semantic reduction $\text{Red}_{PT}: PTEnv \rightarrow PTEnv$ to sharpen the abstract transformers by only keeping states in every pointer has at least one target:

$$\text{Red}_{PT}(pt) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \exists p \in PTLocal. pt(p) = \emptyset ? \perp_{PT} : pt \text{ and } PT[cmd] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} PTv[cmd] \circ \text{Red}_{PT} .$$

$$\begin{array}{ll} PTv[x := aexp] pt &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} pt & PTv[\text{assume}(x \bowtie y)] pt &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} pt \\ PTv[p := \text{NULL}] pt &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} pt[p \mapsto \{ \tau_N \}] & PTv[\text{assume}(p = \text{NULL})] pt &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} pt[p \mapsto pt(p) \cap \{ \tau_N \}] \\ PTv[p := q + i] pt &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} pt[p \mapsto pt(q)] & PTv[\text{assume}(p \neq \text{NULL})] pt &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} pt[p \mapsto pt(p) \setminus \{ \tau_N \}] \\ PTv[x := p - q] pt &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} pt[p \mapsto \mathfrak{R}_{pq}, q \mapsto \mathfrak{R}_{pq}] & PTv[\text{assume}(p = q)] pt &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} pt[p \mapsto pt(p) \cap pt(q), \\ &\text{where } \mathfrak{R}_{pq} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (pt(p) \setminus \{ \tau_N \}) \cap pt(q) & & q \mapsto pt(p) \cap pt(q)] \\ & & PTv[\text{assume}(p \neq q)] pt &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} pt[p \mapsto pt(p) \setminus \mathfrak{R}_q, q \mapsto pt(q) \setminus \mathfrak{R}_p] \\ & & &\text{where } \mathfrak{R}_p \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} pt(p) = \{ \tau_N \} ? \{ \tau_N \} : \emptyset \\ & & &\mathfrak{R}_q \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} pt(q) = \{ \tau_N \} ? \{ \tau_N \} : \emptyset \\ PTv[p := \text{alloc}(s)] pt &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} pt[p \mapsto \{ \tau_K \}] & & \\ PTv[\text{store}(p, v)] pt &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} pt[p \mapsto pt(p) \setminus \{ \tau_N \}] & & \\ PTv[x := \text{load}(p)] pt &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} pt[p \mapsto pt(p) \setminus \{ \tau_N \}] & PTv[\text{ok}(p, s)] pt &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} pt[p \mapsto pt(p) \setminus \{ \tau_K, \tau_N \}] \\ PTv[q := \text{load}(p)] pt &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} pt[q \mapsto ARegs \setminus \mathfrak{R}_{*p}, p \mapsto pt(p) \setminus \{ \tau_N \}] & PTv[\text{notok}(p, s)] pt &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} pt[p \mapsto pt(p) \setminus \{ \tau_K, \tau_N \}] \\ &\text{where } \mathfrak{R}_{*p} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \tau_K \notin pt(p) ? \tau_K : \emptyset & & \end{array}$$

Fig. 7. Vanilla abstract transformers for the region analysis. *ok* stands for `read_ok` and `write_ok`, and *notok* stands for `read_notok` and `write_notok`.

Example 4. The only non-trivial pointer operation in our running example (Fig. 2) is the assignment of f to q (line 3). The context assumptions ensure that f points to a user-space buffer. As f is the only pointer parameter, our analysis deduces that both f and q point to the same buffer.

Theorem 2 (Soundness). *For every command cmd and every abstract region environment pt , we have that the following holds: $\llbracket cmd \rrbracket(\gamma_{PT}(pt)) \subseteq \gamma_{PT}(PT\llbracket cmd \rrbracket(pt))$.*

6.2 Offset Analysis

Our specifications are defined via numeric (integer) constraints over the set of variables $IntVars \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} ILocal \cup Sizes \cup Offset$. In order to infer these numeric constraints, we employ a numeric analysis of integers, which is defined over the set of *integer environments* $ZEnv \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} IntVars \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$. We can extract integer environments from instrumented states via the operation $InstToZEnv : \hat{\Sigma} \rightarrow ZEnv$, where

$$InstToZEnv(\langle n, env, h, A, R, W \rangle) = env|_{IntVars}.$$

We assume we are given a numeric abstract domain $ZDom[V] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \langle \Gamma, \perp_z, \sqcup_z, \nabla_z \rangle$, parameterized by a set of numeric variables V , and optionally equipped with a widening operation ∇_z to ensure the convergence of the static analysis. We will instantiate the numeric domain with $IntVars$, and simply write $ZDom$ for $ZDom[IntVars]$, and range over it using \mathbf{z} . We assume that $ZDom$ is equipped with the following operations:

- A single-state abstraction function $\beta_z : ZEnv \rightarrow \Gamma$;
- A concretization function $\gamma_z : \Gamma \rightarrow \wp(ZEnv)$;
- Sound abstract transformers $Z\llbracket cmd \rrbracket : \Gamma \rightarrow \Gamma$ for the commands $x := aexp$ and **assume**($x \bowtie y$).
- An operation $Z\llbracket x := \top \rrbracket$, which removes all constraints on variable x , thus forgetting any information on its value;
- An operation $Z\llbracket x := \perp \rrbracket$, which, when applied to \mathbf{z} , removes x from the domain of \mathbf{z} , and thus ensures that \mathbf{z} cannot represent environments in which x is defined;
- A constraint-extraction operation $CONSTRAINTS_z : \Gamma \rightarrow \Phi$, discussed in §7, which converts numeric abstract states to the format required by the symbolic execution engine.

We use the numeric domain to define a single-state abstraction function $\beta_{Num} : \hat{\Sigma} \rightarrow \Gamma$ and concretization function $\gamma_{Num} : \Gamma \rightarrow \wp(\hat{\Sigma})$ for instrumented states as follows:

$$\beta_{Num} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} InstToZEnv \circ \beta_z \quad \gamma_{Num}(\mathbf{z}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{\delta \mid \beta_{Num}(\delta) \sqcup_z \mathbf{z} = \mathbf{z}\}.$$

For every command cmd , let $\text{Inst}[cmd] = \llbracket cmd \rrbracket \circ \text{Inst}'[cmd]$ be the corresponding instrumented semantics transformer. We define the abstract transformers $\text{Off}[cmd] : \Gamma \rightarrow \Gamma$, for every command cmd in our language as follows:

$$\text{Off}[cmd] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \begin{cases} Z[x := \top], & cmd = x := \text{load}(p); \\ \text{ld}, & cmd = \text{assume}(p = q); \\ \text{ld}, & cmd = \text{assume}(p \neq q); \\ Z[\hat{cmd}], & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

That is, we apply the numeric analysis transformers to the numeric commands, whereas load commands and pointer comparisons are handled conservatively.

Theorem 3 (Soundness). *For every command cmd and every numeric abstract state $\mathbf{z} \in \Gamma$, we have that the following holds: $\llbracket cmd \rrbracket(\gamma_{\text{Num}}(\mathbf{z})) \subseteq \gamma_{\text{Num}}(\text{Off}[cmd](\mathbf{z}))$.*

6.3 Combined Region-Offset Analysis

Our analysis operates over the product domain $Comb \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} PT\text{Dom} \times Z\text{Dom}$, where each operation is defined component-wise.⁷ Abstraction α_{Comb} and concretization γ_{Comb} are defined in the standard way for a product domain, i.e., $\gamma_{Comb}(\langle pt, \mathbf{z} \rangle) = \gamma_{PT}(pt) \cap \gamma_{\mathbf{z}}(\mathbf{z})$.

For every command cmd , other than pointer comparison and memory validation, the abstract transformers apply the transformer for each individual domain and then the semantic reduction $\text{Red} : (PT\text{Env} \times Z\text{Env}) \rightarrow (PT\text{Env} \times Z\text{Env})$, which projects out offset variables for pointers that do not reference the respective buffer:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket cmd \rrbracket^\# \langle pt, \mathbf{z} \rangle &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{Red}(\langle \text{PT}[cmd](pt), \text{Off}[cmd](\mathbf{z}) \rangle) \\ \text{Red}(pt, \mathbf{z}) &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \langle pt, \mathbf{z}[offset_{p,f} \mapsto \perp \mid f \notin pt(p)] \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

In the sequel, we use the shorthand $pt' = \text{PT}[cmd](pt)$ and $\mathbf{z}' = \text{Off}[cmd](\mathbf{z})$ for every command cmd .

Pointer comparisons can be handled more precisely when both pointers are known to reference the same buffer, thus we do a case analysis based on the possible buffer they may point to:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \text{assume}(p = q) \rrbracket^\# \langle pt, \mathbf{z} \rangle &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{Red} \left(\langle pt'_{\{\tau_K, \tau_U, \tau_N\}}, \mathbf{z}'_{\{\tau_K, \tau_U, \tau_N\}} \rangle \right) \\ &\quad \bigsqcup_{\tau_f \in ABuffers} \bigsqcup_{PT} \text{Red} \left(\langle pt'_{\{\tau_f\}}, \text{Off}[\text{assume}(offset_{f,p} = offset_{f,q})] \mathbf{z}'_{\{\tau_f\}} \rangle \right) \\ \text{where } pt'_{\mathfrak{R}} &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} pt'[p \mapsto pt'(p) \cap \mathfrak{R}, q \mapsto pt'(q) \cap \mathfrak{R}] \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{z}'_{\mathfrak{R}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbf{z}'[offset_{f,p} \mapsto \perp, offset_{f,q} \mapsto \perp \mid \tau_f \notin \mathfrak{R}] \\ \llbracket \text{assume}(p \neq q) \rrbracket^\# \langle pt, \mathbf{z} \rangle &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \exists f \in PT\text{Formal}. pt'(p) = pt'(q) = \{\tau_f\} ? \langle pt', \mathbf{z}'_f \rangle : \langle pt', \mathbf{z}' \rangle \\ \text{where } \mathbf{z}'_f &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{Off}[\text{assume}(offset_{f,p} \neq offset_{f,q})] \end{aligned}$$

To handle memory validation commands, we case-split for the different targets of the pointer p —either a location in the user-space, NULL, or any buffer—then handle each case under the respective assumption, and finally join the

⁷ Since the region abstract domain is finite, we define widening by join.

results. (Below, *ok* stands for `read_ok` and `write_ok`, and *notok* stands for `read_notok` and `write_notok`.)

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket ok(p, s) \rrbracket^\#(pt, \mathbf{z}) &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{Red}(\langle pt'[p \mapsto pt'(p) \cap \{\tau_U\}], \mathbf{z}' \rangle) \sqcup \bigsqcup_{f \in PTFormal} \text{Red}(\langle pt'[p \mapsto pt'(p) \cap \{\tau_f\}], \zeta(\mathbf{z}') \rangle) \\ \zeta(\mathbf{z}') &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{Off}[\text{assume}(\text{offset}_{f,p} + \hat{s} < \text{size}_f)](\mathbf{z}') \\ \llbracket notok(p, s) \rrbracket^\#(pt, \mathbf{z}) &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{Red}(\langle pt'[p \mapsto pt'(p) \cap \{\tau_U, \tau_N\}], \mathbf{z}' \rangle) \sqcup \bigsqcup_{f \in PTFormal} \text{Red}(\langle pt'[p \mapsto pt'(p) \cap \{\tau_f\}], \eta(\mathbf{z}') \rangle) \\ \eta(\mathbf{z}') &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{Off}[\text{assume}(\text{offset}_{f,p} + \hat{s} \geq \text{size}_f)](\mathbf{z}') \end{aligned}$$

```

GENERATECONTRACT(Analysis :  $N \rightarrow (PTEnv \times \Gamma)$ )
  emit "contract_{\varphi_{init}} {"
  // Generating auxiliary variables
  emit "int lLocal+ \ IFormal;"
  foreach f \in PTFormal do
    emit "uint size_f;"
    emit "int offset_{f,f};"
  emit "long res;"
  // 1. Auxiliary variable initialization
  foreach f \in PTFormal do
    emit "size_f = SE_size_obj(f);"
    emit "offset_{f,f} = f - SE_base(f);"
  // 2. Detecting memory errors
  foreach n \in N_{notok} do
    (pt, z) = Analysis(n)
    if \tau_N \in pt(ptr(n)) emit "warn('nullderef error!');"
    if \tau_U \in pt(ptr(n)) emit "warn('buffer overrun!');"
    emit "if SE_SAT(" + CONSTRAINTS_z(z) + ") +
        "warn('buffer overrun!');"
  // 3. Generating modifies clauses
  foreach n \in N_{writeok} do
    (pt, z) = Analysis(n)
    foreach f \in PTFormal \cap pt(ptr(n)) do
      emit "if SE_SAT(" + CONSTRAINTS_z(z) + ") +
          "SE_havoc_cont(" + f + ");"
  // 4. Generating postconditions
  \phi = false;
  foreach n \in N_{Ret} do
    (pt, z) = Analysis(n)
    \phi = \phi \vee CONSTRAINTS_z(z)
  emit "SE_assume(" + \phi + ");"
  emit "return(res)"
  emit "}"

```

Fig. 8. The contract generation algorithm. `emit` prints out code; `+` denotes string concatenation.

7 Generating Contracts

Our contracts are C procedures integrated into the symbolic execution engine as surrogates for the respective implementations of system calls. Fig. 8 shows our algorithm for converting the result of our static analysis (*Analysis*) into a symbolically-executable contract. The contract generator firsts emits the declarations of the auxiliary variables which store the sizes and offsets of memory regions and pointers, respectively, as local variables of the contract, and declares the return value as a `long`. It then continue to produce the four elements of each contracts described in §3.3.

The generation of the contracts is rather straightforward. After initializing the variables (1), we generate code which warn about possible memory errors (2), havocs any buffer that the kernel might have written to (3), and generates constraints which restricts the possible return values (4). The algorithm utilizes an extraction function which, given the numerical component of an $\mathbf{s} = \langle pt, \mathbf{z} \rangle$, generates a formula $\text{CONSTRAINTS}_{\mathbf{z}}(\mathbf{z})$ describing numerical relations between the values of integer arguments, offsets of pointers, and the sizes of input buffers. The extraction function depends on the numerical domain used. The Polyhedra domain [23], which we use in our implementation, records correlations between numerical variables using a dual representation: either as a conjunction of linear inequalities or as a polyhedron. In this domain, the constraint extraction function merely returns the former representation, after projecting away the local variables.

Example 5. The constrained extracted for \mathbf{s}_{Ret} (see Example 1) are as follows:

$$\begin{array}{l}
\phi_1 = 0 < rv \wedge rv \leq s \wedge rv \leq 512 \\
\phi_2 = 0 \leq \text{offset}_{f,f} \wedge \text{offset}_{f,f} \leq \text{size}_f \\
\phi_4 = res = rv \wedge \text{offset}_{f,q} - \text{offset}_{f,f} = rv \wedge \text{offset}_{f,f} + s < \text{size}_f \\
\hline
\text{CONSTRAINTS}_{\mathbf{z}}(\mathbf{s}_{Ret}) = \text{CONSTRAINTS}_{\mathbf{z}}(\phi_1 \wedge \phi_2 \wedge \phi_4) = \\
0 < s \wedge 0 \leq \text{offset}_{f,f} \wedge \text{offset}_{f,f} + s < \text{size}_f \wedge 0 < res \wedge res \leq s \wedge res \leq 512
\end{array}$$

Context-sensitive Contracts. A context assumption is a formula φ_{init} comprised of a conjunction of linear inequalities over instrumentation variables, where we allow to write $\text{offset}_{f_1, f_2} = \perp$ to denote that the formal parameter f_1 does *not* point to the same region as f_2 . We then use a domain-specific function to convert these assumptions into an abstract state that represents all the instrumented states that satisfy the induced constraints. For the Polyhedra domain, the resulting numerical abstract state is simply φ_{init} . We note that in our experiments, we only needed to use a context in which all the pointer parameters are valid, have non-NULL values, and are not aliased.

8 Additional Case Studies

In this section, we briefly discuss the way our technique can be adapted for symbolic execution of applications using low-level system libraries other than the Linux kernel.

Secure Enclaves. Intel’s Software Guarded Extensions (SGX) is a set of extensions to the Intel architecture that aims to provide integrity and confidentiality guarantees to security-sensitive computation performed on a computer where all the privileged software (kernel, hypervisor, etc.) is potentially malicious [21]. Roughly speaking, SGX allows to execute library code inside *secure enclaves*, which are memory regions inaccessible to any code, including the operating system, but that of the library. This makes the library code and data temper proof. We can utilize this programming model as it provides a clear interface between

the library memory and the application memory. In fact, Intel guidelines recommend to copy in and out all data that passes between the enclave and the user application. In most cases, this is done automatically by the compiler via `in`, `out`, and `inout`, annotations, which specify the accessed regions. However, as the enclave’s memory is rather small, the library programmer may wish to perform this transfer explicitly in a piecewise manner or even access the application memory directly when the buffer parameters are particularly large. In these cases, to prevent corruption of the enclave memory by malicious applications, the guidelines instruct to invoke the `sgx_is_outside_enclave(p,s)` function, which verifies that the memory region it intends to access ($p \dots p + s$) is outside the enclave. Our analysis leverages this memory protection mechanism to identify the buffers that library reads from (`in` parameters) and writes to (`out` and `inout`) and explicitly verified buffers as (possibly) written buffers. Note that, unlike the Linux kernel, there is no fixed set of interface functions—every library has its own interface.

Openssl’s BIO interface. The *BIO* library [50] provides an abstract interface to the *openssl* library [51], which allows to write composable filters. The filters hide cryptographic operations behind a stream read/write interface. By inferring the specification of the read and write functions of this API, e.g., of filters that perform encryption and decryption, we can have the symbolic execution skip over the cryptographic code, which is notoriously difficult for symbolic execution. The filter accesses to the application’s memory using *read* and *write* primitives. For example, the *encryption* filter uses `enc_read` and `enc_write` operations. Our analysis leverages these functions to identify the user buffers accessed by the library.

libc. Many applications do not invoke system calls directly. Instead, they utilize it via C standard library (`libc`). In our evaluation (§9), we noticed that the symbolic execution of `libc`’s functions, which read and write to files, is very time-consuming because our contracts return a symbolic value for the number of bytes they read (resp. write). This leads the SE engine to fork many states that differ by the number of times the system call was invoked to consume all the input. These distinctions, however, are irrelevant from the viewpoint of the client applications. Thus, we applied our analysis to infer contracts for that `_stdio_read` and `_stdio_write` functions, using the contract of the system call they invoke to determine their effect. We then created `SCIIOKLEE`, a variant `SCIKLEE`, which uses the contracts of these two functions instead of their implementations.

Caveats The *BIO* library as well as the `libc` library provide clients with opaque library-allocated handles. These are pointers to library state that the client is expected not to modify. For example, the *BIO* library uses `BIO*` handles and the `libc` library uses `FILE*` handles. Our analysis does not support this paradigm. Thus, we manually annotated these handles as library pointers. Extending our analysis to support handle-based programming and extending the SE engine to

check that client applications do not access the opaque handles is a matter of future work.

9 Implementation and Experimental Results

We implemented our approach for symbolic execution with contracts in SCIKLEE, a publicly available modified version of KLEE which we adapted to expose the necessary SE services (see Fig. 3). We implemented our static analysis in the LLVM [45] framework using the Parma Polyhedra Library version 1097 [11]. We conducted our experiments on a commodity PC with a quad core 3.40 GHz Intel Core i7-6700U processor and 32GB memory running 64-bit Ubuntu Linux version 14.04. We used STP 2.1.2 as the constraint solver [27].

Our main case study involves four applications and seven application suites which make extensive use of the Linux Kernel system call interface. We evaluated the precision and efficiency of our approach using two typical applications of symbolic execution: *bug finding* and *code coverage*. We note that our objective is not to establish the superiority of our technique for any specific task—and thus omits a direct comparison with other state-of-the-art techniques for each scenario—but rather to assess the attainable benefits of utilizing the inferred specifications in symbolic execution.

9.1 Inferring Linux System Calls Specifications

We analyzed all 327 system calls of the Linux kernel version 3.19.0. The analysis took 1559 seconds, where the most expensive analysis with respect to time and memory usage were of *getrandom* (116 seconds) and *advise* (3.6GB). The inferred contracts are conjunctions of constraints. The contract for 114 system calls was *true*. This happens in e.g., *fchown*, which gets no user pointers, and its return value is calculated in an internal function which is not analyzed. Therefore, the contract does not have any constraints. The other contracts has between 1 and 63 conjuncts, where the average number was 7.8 and 48 contracts contained eight or more conjuncts.

The aforementioned results shows that our analysis is scalable and can produce non-trivial contracts. However, the scalability had a price: The return value of *read*, *readv*, *write*, *writev*, and *gethostbyname* is capped by the amount of data read or written. Our analysis could not have inferred this information because it is computed by kernel functions which we do not analyze. Thus, to prevent many false alarms, we encoded this knowledge into the contracts of these system calls by manually adding a conjunct which says that the return value is capped by the size of the user buffer. (The other contracts were not modified.) We believe that such minor precision improvement operations are to be expected due to the limitation of static analysis algorithms.

9.2 Symbolic Execution of User Applications using Contracts for Linux System Calls

We evaluated our technique using the four applications and seven application suites listed in Fig. 9. The figure shows the version and size, measured in lines of C code (LoC), of each benchmark, the number of distinct programs in each applications suite (#Bins), and the number of times SCIKLEE invoked a contracts (#Syscalls). Our benchmarks include `coreutils` (GNU’s suite of core utilities), KLEE’s poster child benchmarking suite as well as a heavy user of *C* standard library, as it would be remarkable to find new bugs in its programs using symbolic execution as well as to increase its code coverage. The other benchmarks, described below, are mature, well tested, networking utilities. Thus, we expected that detecting bugs in these applications to be challenging. Furthermore, KLEE does not support networking commands despite being applied to system programs for years. Thus, analyzing these applications, described below, showcases the benefits of utilizing automatically inferred specifications of low level complicated libraries.

- `thttpd` is a small, portable, fast, and secure HTTP server.
- `netcat` is a feature-packed networking utility which reads and writes data across TCP/IP network connections, designed to be driven reliably by other programs and scripts.
- `inetutils` provides common networking utilities, clients, and servers of the GNU Operating System. It contains applications such as `ping` and `ping6` and `ftp` and `telnet` clients and servers.
- `binutils` contains various compilers, assemblers, linkers, debuggers, etc.
- `moreutils` a collection of unix tools.
- `ntpclient` is a simple, lightweight client of the Network Time Protocol (NTP) version 4.
- `ntp` is an NTP version 4 distribution. It includes sophisticated implementations of an NTP client and server, as well as some other networking utilities.
- `dnsmasq` provides network services, such as DHCP and DNS servers, for small networks.
- `isc-dhcp` is the Internet Systems Consortium DHCP Distribution.
- `isc-bind` is a complete, highly portable implementation of the DNS protocol.

Methodology. We compiled our benchmarks to LLVM bitcode and analyzed them using three KLEE, SCIKLEE, and SCIOKLEE. Applications were invoked with n command line arguments, where $n < 10$ is symbolic and each argument is a symbolic string of maximum length 10. We analyzed each of the 47 applications for one hour by each tool. The examined applications invokes system calls via the `libc` standard library. When running KLEE, we used the standard *C* library included in its distribution (a modified version of `uclibc` [6] with a hand-crafted model of several system calls). When running SCIKLEE we used the more modern `musl` library [48]. Here, we symbolically executed the library code and used the generated contracts when system calls were invoked. We did the same when

running SCIIOKLEE except that we used the inferred contracts of `_stdio_read` and `_stdio_write` instead of symbolically executing them (see §8).

Benchmark		#Syscalls			Coverage (%)					Alarms (True and False)						
App/Suite	Version	LoC	#Bins	sciKlee	Klee	sciKlee	Total	sciOKlee	Total ^{IO}	Klee	sciKlee	sciOKlee				
thttpd	2.27	8,357	1	3,262	0.27	2.55	2.56	2.49	2.49		1T		1T			
netcat	1.10-41	1,836	1	6,929	1.06	3.62	3.62	12.98	12.98		1T		1T			
inetutils	1.9.4-2	116,902	20	528,480	40.31	19.37	41.37	33.61	44.64	1T	5T	4F	5T	4F		
ntpclient	2015_365	915	1	9,765	7.54	2.62	7.54	18.78	18.78			1F	1T	3F		
ntp	dev-4.3.93	244,946	8	89,145	2.18	3.05	4.08	5.25	6.08	1F		1F		1F		
dnsmasq	2.77	29,178	1	482,451	1.32	0.2	1.34	0.22	1.36							
isc-dhcp	4.3.6	434,560	6	169,719	0.83	0.34	0.92	0.49	1.03							
isc-bind	9.11.2	398,653	9	394,028	0.46	0.25	0.49	0.45	0.60							
coreutils	8.27	20,2127	64	1,763,422	23.48	11.53	24.24	24.81	27.61							
moreutils	0.61	2,455	8	10,462	36.22	31.63	43.06	53.18	56.47	1T	2F	1T	6F	1T	6F	
binutils	2.30.51	2,388,047	14	19,863	0.51	0.35	0.59	0.89	0.98		3F		2F		3F	
<i>total</i>		<i>3,827,976</i>	<i>133</i>	<i>3,477,526</i>							<i>2T</i>	<i>6F</i>	<i>8T</i>	<i>14F</i>	<i>9T</i>	<i>16F</i>

Fig. 9. Benchmark applications and experimental results.

Symbolic Execution with Contracts for Bug Finding Fig. 9 shows the number of true and false alarms raised by each tool. The nine real bugs found by SCIIOKLEE and the 16 false alarms it raised include the eight real bugs found by SCIKLEE and the 14 false alarms it raised, which, in turn, include the two real bugs and six false alarms raised by KLEE. In addition, SCIKLEE found two real bugs in *musl*, and produced a single false alarm. The results show that the use of contracts greatly improves the ability to find real bugs with a reasonable penalty regarding additional false alarms.

Bugs found. Below, we review four interesting bugs we found.

- **thttpd** does not verify the return value of *getcwd*. However, if *getcwd* fails, it does not initialize its input buffer. This leads to a buffer overrun by a string-manipulating function.
- In **netcat**, a casting error of the result of a *read* operation may lead to a buffer overrun error.⁸
- **ntpclient** invokes *recvfrom* with a pointer to a variable containing the size of the input buffer, but does not reset it between calls. As *recvfrom* is allowed to modify the size variable to a greater value, subsequent calls to *recvfrom* may write beyond the end of the buffer.
- In **inetutils**, *hostname* does not verify the return value of a function which may cause a NULL-pointer dereference. That function parses a file, and the bug appears only when the file has specific content. Additionally, the contents of the file is copied to a dynamically allocated buffer, but the buffer is allocated with no room for the zero-terminator, causing an out-of-bounds write. In some cases, parsing fails, but the buffer is returned to the caller, containing uninitialized data. (These bugs were reported and fixed.)

⁸ To reach this bug in a reasonable time, the constant *BIGSIZ* had to be decreased from 8192 to 512. *BIGSIZ* controls the size of big buffers allocated by *netcat*, and indirectly the depth of loops operating on these buffers.

False Alarms. We now discuss the main causes of the false alarms raised by our tools. Our static analysis fails to detect that the error return values of *read* and *write*, produced by an unanalyzed kernel functions, are between -1 and -512. Unfortunately, *musl* fails to detect error codes below -4096. Therefore, SCIKLEE conservatively reports an out-of-bound memory access. Another source for false alarms is due to an imprecise analysis of strings. Specifically, false positives arise when the application expects to get a zero-terminated string while the system call contract does not enforce it. This happens, e.g., with *uname*, *symlinkat*, and *readlink*. We note that we could have eliminated these errors by tweaking the automatically generated contracts to record this information.

Symbolic Execution with Contracts for Increasing Code Coverage

Fig. 9 shows the percentage of the lines of code covered by each tool. Judging each tool on its own, the results are rather mixed: In some applications KLEE covered significantly more instructions than SCIKLEE, e.g., *dnsmasq*, whereas in others SCIKLEE and SCIOKLEE, *netcat*, had the upper hand. (Interestingly, SCIOKLEE covered more instructions than KLEE in *coreutils*.) However, when we consider the gains obtained when our method is used to *supplement* KLEE, the picture becomes more clear: Fig. 9 also shows the percentage of lines of code covered by either KLEE or SCIKLEE (Total) and by KLEE or SCIOKLEE (Total^O). Note that the combined coverage in all of our benchmarks is greater than the cover obtained by each method separately. This means that KLEE and our tools cover partially disjoint parts of the application. Hence, our approach is beneficial when it comes to extending the code coverage obtained by symbolic execution.

In some experiments, the gains obtained by our tools over KLEE were particularly impressive (even though overall coverage for all methods was mostly rather poor). For example, in the analysis of *dhclient*, *dhcrelay*, and *andomshell* (coming from the *isc-dhcp* application suite) SCIKLEE covered *x12*, *x13*, and *x4* more instructions than KLEE. Even more impressive results were obtained in the analysis of *ntpdate*, *ntpdc*, *ntpq*, *propdelay* and *sntp* (coming from the *isc-dhcp* application suite), where SCIKLEE covered *x18*, *x52*, *x51*, *x26*, and *x15* more instructions than KLEE. SCIOKLEE obtained particularly impressive results when analyzing *named* (coming from the *isc-bind* application suite), where it covered *x10* more instruction than either KLEE or SCIKLEE. In many cases, these gains were achieved because many of the analyzed utilities begin by initializing network elements, e.g. checking for IPv4 or IPv6 capabilities. KLEE does not support these functions, and terminates the branch with an error, whereas SCIKLEE can continue. In contrast, KLEE covered more instructions than our tools when it was able to leverage its more precise modeling of the file system. In particular, when the application read concrete files, KLEE was able to continue the symbolic execution with concrete values whereas our contracts returned a symbolic value for the contents of the file. This hints that extending our technique to perform system calls instead of invoking its contracts can make it even more competitive.

9.3 Additional Experiments

Secure Enclaves. We applied our analysis to infer the symbolic execution-suitable specifications for *wolfssl*—a small, fast, portable implementation of TLS/SSL for embedded devices to the cloud [66], which can run inside secure enclaves. We used the inferred specification to perform symbolic execution of the library’s example application [65], which is comprised of 344 lines. The coverage percentages of KLEE, SCIKLEE, and SCIIOKLEE are, respectively: 14.11%, 9.91%, and 32.7% , and of KLEE together with SCIKLEE (resp. SCIIOKLEE) are 15.43% (resp. 31.40%).

Openssl’s BIO interface. We evaluated the contracts produced by our analysis by symbolically executing *bio_enc.test*, a unit test available in the *openssl* repository. The test has 181 lines. The coverage percentages of the test and *openssl* code for KLEE, SCIKLEE, and SCIIOKLEE were, respectively: 0.86%, 0.43%, and 1.63%, and of KLEE together with SCIKLEE (resp. SCIIOKLEE) are 0.91% (resp. 1.8%).

10 Related Work

Symbolic execution has a long successful history as an automated technique for bug finding and test generation (see, e.g., [16]). In this section, we review closely related work.

Prior work extensively investigated the idea of making symbolic execution scale leveraging procedural abstractions. Swarat et al. [2] suggest a compositional analysis using under-approximation: the analyzers create precise procedure summaries out of a selection of intra-procedural executions which capture some, but not all, behaviors of the callee. These summaries are then combined to create inter-procedural executions of their clients. In [29], symbolic execution on a program is also done compositionally. Each procedure symbolically executed separately, and a summary is generated. When the caller is analyzed, the summary is used instead of analyzing the called procedure. This greatly reduces the analysis complexity. In contrast, we use static analysis to generate contract which over-approximate the behavior of the analyzed procedures . This allows avoiding performing symbolic execution of library code all together.

Scalability is improved in [59] by running under-constrained symbolic execution, a variation of symbolic execution. By running on individual procedures, rather than whole programs, they greatly reduce the search space and avoid path explosion. However, their variant is limited to verifying that new changes do not add bugs, and comparing different versions of the same function. LATEST [46] replaces function calls with symbolic values, to increase the coverage in the caller. If a bug is found, the symbolic execution is re-run with the original function. However, LATEST assumes that the library has not have side-effects on the client’s memory. In [31], the author proposes to replace functions that cannot be handled by the solver (e.g., the code is unavailable, or too complex)

with uninterpreted functions, thus improving the overall coverage of symbolic and concolic execution. Here, again, handling side-effects is tricky.

SMART [30] performs compositional test generation by computing summaries of all program functions. The summary of a function is computed by exploring all paths of the function using DSE and then by merging the symbolic states of those paths via symbolic auxiliary variables. For real programs, SMART can generate function summaries that are outside the theories that can be handled by an SMT solver, which simplifies the summaries at the cost of completeness. Demand-driven compositional symbolic execution [3] was subsequently proposed to incrementally construct partial summaries to avoid analyzing unnecessary paths in functions. SMASH [33] incorporates both symbolic execution summaries (must summaries) and static analysis summaries (may summaries). SMASH performs reachability analysis to reason about possible buggy program states and to prune out group of uninteresting execution paths. Our work increases the coverage of symbolic execution by replacing the implementation of system calls with contracts that, from the symbolic execution engine’s perspective, behave the same as the system call. However, it is unique in the way it infers the specifications using design assumptions.

The challenge of handling the effect of system calls has been addressed in existing literature by supplying a model of the operating system. For example, [14] deploy models for certain aspects of system’s libraries, e.g., file handling in standard C libraries. The models, however, do not cover the entire C library and the lack of models for, e.g., network operations, precludes the analysis of programs that use the Internet. Changing or extending the model requires a significant (and error-prone) effort from tool builders. In contrast, our system automatically infers conservative specifications of system calls, allowing to test the program against different versions of the standard library. This flexibility, however, comes with a cost: The symbolic execution engine has to *execute* the code of the standard libraries.

The problem of overapproximating procedure summaries using static analysis has been heavily addressed e.g., [17, 38, 54, 60]. Essentially, existing works, ours included, compute an overapproximation of the procedure’s input output relation. The main challenge is often the treatment of indirect memory accesses via pointers. Our solution to this problem is uniquely designed to benefit from the way system’s code is written. This is reflected both in our concrete semantics and abstract interpretation. For example, one big issue in summarizing procedures addressed in [26] is the treatment of may-pointer aliases. Fortunately, we can focus on a bounded number of memory regions (the buffers) allowing us to compute rather precise procedure summaries at a moderate cost.

PASKET [39] uses sample code, as provided by tutorials in the documentation, to identify known design patterns used in the code, and generate a model that can be used to symbolic execution. The approach in [1] is somewhat reversed, in that symbolic execution is used to generate the model of a cryptographic C program, and then verify it using protocol analyzers e.g. ProVerif. OCSEGen [64] generates a model of a Java libraries by breaking them down to

small units and modeling each unit separately. In addition to static analysis, e.g., pointer analysis, the modeling can be done also by user specification. In our experience, pointer analysis of low level system code may produce very inaccurate results. In [18], a model of a library is generated automatically via slicing: The analysis specifies which fields of library objects it considers, and their tool uses this information to slice away irrelevant code. This approach can indeed be very helpful when considering libraries written in high-level languages as Java. However, applying it to low level system code such as the Linux Kernel can be very difficult due to the impression of the pointer analysis. These two solutions are used in [47] to model the Android application framework and library for verification. Our method is similar in that it slices away the *deep* kernel code, and runs static analysis only on the user-space API layer. In contrast, we provide a mechanism to compute an

In [52], it was noticed that most of the errors in the kernel arrive from driver code. Unfortunately, static analysis on kernel code is very difficult due its the prolific use of pointers in kernel code. To work around this, some tools target specific bugs. Unisan [44] target data leakages, ESP [24] concentrates on `printf` usage, and [10] specifically verifies user memory access validation in system calls. In contrast, we expect that the kernel is implemented correctly, without attempting to prove it. The work in [10] can be used in tandem to verify our assumptions.

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